

PATCH ANTENNA DEVELOPMENT METHODOLOGY

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Abstract – Microstrip patch antennas are used in a variety of wireless applications, such as smartphones, radars, GPS systems, and IoT devices. Due to their advantages, such as portability, affordable cost, and ease of prototyping, this antenna was developed to be applied to Wi-Fi routers, helping and facilitating the increase in signal range. This methodology and development process allows for an accurate assessment of the antenna's electromagnetic characteristics, helping to develop more efficient and effective solutions for wireless communication. With these studies, we seek not only to increase signal range, but also to ensure better performance and better availability and quality of the connection for users.

Key-words: Patch Antenna, Microstrip, IoT, GPS, Wi-Fi.

INTRODUCTION

Microstrip patch antennas have gained prominence in recent years due to their versatility, low profile and ease of manufacture, finding wide application in mobile communication systems, radars and global positioning systems (GPS) [1]. Among the various geometries and configurations, rectangular patch antennas are the most common due to their simplicity of design and analysis.

This work aims to design, build and characterize a rectangular microstrip patch antenna, a technology widely used in several communication systems due to its practicality and low cost [2]. The antenna will be manufactured using an FR-4 phenolic substrate and designed to operate in the 2.2GHz band.

A conventional microstrip antenna generally requires an electrically thin substrate, thus presenting a narrow bandwidth [3].

The physical antenna will be built using conventional printed circuit board manufacturing techniques and will then be experimentally characterized to verify its performance.

The results obtained in the simulations and experimental tests will be compared to evaluating the accuracy of the model and identifying possible discrepancies.

DEVELOPMENT

All parameters and dimensions of the patch antenna were initially obtained through an algorithm developed using the Scilab platform, parameterizing with the values of the input variables (Fig. 1).

Input the desired input impedance Z_{in} (ohms) = 50

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"INPUT PARAMETERS =====
Resonant frequency = 2.20 GHz
Dielectric constant of the substrate = 4.30
Height of the substrate = 1.60 mm
Desired resonant input impedance = 50.00 ohms
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"OUTPUT PARAMETERS =====
Microstrip line feed width (Wfeed) = 3.13 mm
Physical width (W) of patch = 41.88 mm
Effective length (Leff) of patch = 34.02 mm
Physical length (L) of patch = 32.54 mm
E-PLANE HPBW = 180.00 degrees
H-PLANE HPBW = 180.00 degrees
Antenna ABS directivity = 4.03
Antenna directivity = 6.06 dB
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Figure 1 – Patch antenna parameters and topology obtained using an algorithm developed in Scilab.

Initially, the antenna design was converted into a Gerber file, as shown in Fig. 2, which was used to manufacture the printed circuit board.

Figure 2 – Project Design in QucsStudio 4

Using the QucsStudio 4 platform, the signal generated by the antenna was also simulated and the graph of the antenna input impedance as a function of frequency was obtained, obtaining an antenna resonance frequency of 2.35 GHz, with a minimum reflection coefficient (S11) of -15.77 dB, as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3 - Antenna input impedance vs. frequency graph generated by QucsStudio 4

The FR-4 phenolic substrate, with dielectric constant $\epsilon_r = 4.3$ and thickness $h = 1.6$ mm, was cut to the specified dimensions: patch width $W = 42$ mm and length $L = 32$ mm. The metallic pattern of the antenna was etched onto the board using a copper tape made with a utility knife, as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4 – Patch antenna prototype

The FR-4 phenolic substrate, with dielectric constant $\epsilon_r = 4.3$ and thickness $h = 1.6$ mm, was cut to the specified dimensions: patch width $W = 42$ mm and length $L = 32$ mm. The metallic pattern of the antenna was etched onto the board using a copper tape made with a utility knife, as shown in Fig. 4.

High performance can be achieved by integrating the patch antenna into the low dielectric constant material with thick thickness [4].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Fig. 5 shows the plot of the antenna input impedance as a function of frequency. The antenna resonance frequency was 2.38 GHz, with a minimum reflection coefficient (S11) of -19 dB.

Figure 5 - Antenna input impedance graph as a function of frequency generated by the GS-320 model signal analyzer and Arinst VNA software

Tab. 1 shows the values obtained in the simulation and experiment.

Table 1 – Results obtained

Parameter	Simulated Value	Experimental Value
Resonance Frequency (GHz)	2,35	2,38
Minimum Reflection Coefficient (S11) (dB)	-15,77	-19

Source: The Authors (2024)

With the results presented in this article, it is possible to meet the most varied technologies in Patch antennas operating at professional performance in a frequency range with high availability. It was proven that the geometries designed in this article, based on techniques previously described, can validate the use of patch antennas. Considering the importance of antennas with characteristics that enhance transmissions, it is crucial to carry out studies and develop new geometries. One segment that has aroused great interest is that of antennas with dual operating bands [3].

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